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Sample Name: Proszki

C

eZAF Quant Result - Analysis Uncertainty: 6.77 %

Element	Weight %	MDL	Atomic %	Error %
C K	97.5	0.02	98.1	5.0
O K	2.5	0.03	1.9	11.6

/Lukasiewicz 25.02.25/Proszki/C/Full Area 1/

kV: 5 Mag: 500 Takeoff: 35.5 Live Time(s): 300 Amp Time(μs): 0.96 Resolution:(eV) 131.6

